

TOWARD A THEORY OF MOTHER - DAUGHTER RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ARABIC AND ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This communication attempts to answer the question regarding the origin or the mother of the English as a Germanic language. Many scholars have attempted to find out the answer calling the original language the “Indo- European” language but never substantiated and resolved it. The researcher is proposing new theory claiming the mother language is the Arabic language not accepting the evidences in the form of cognates to be a simple borrowing relationship between Arabic to English or accidental similarities. The researcher provided the following cognate systems to substantiate the theory; a large shared vocabulary, kin words, pronoun systems, body parts, names of animals, linguistic evidence, old property and items, names which do not change over time.

Keywords: relationship, borrowing, origin

1. Introduction

Many linguists have been interested in attempting to find out about the origin of the English language, a world lingua franca which is bringing the world together. Some Arab linguists documented in special dictionaries reaching around 25,000 recognizable Arabic words in the English language. The attached annex 1 includes words of similar characteristics. This paper tackles the relationship between Arabic and English as a Germanic language from an origin point of view while most linguists and experts talk about it from a borrowing point of view citing the similarities in meaning and pronunciation between English and Arabic words as a vocabulary cognate system such as: [solid-sugar-assert-crown-sun-ascend-camera-stand-Hashish-mug-tariff-jar-check-guide-cover-guess-noble-banana-magazine-cipher-safari-Helilolya-Gladiator-usher-Poor-Honey-Tall-Mass-Cut-Pupil-Nag-good-cave-sesame-mirror-summit-mechanic-friction-isolation-Captain-Alcohol-merge-Dunk-mesmerize-candy-case-syrup-spinach-coffee-garble-sofa-mattress-jumper-orange-and medicine transliterated from the

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Arabic words *madacine* (Iviccine material) which are easy to relate to a historic period as borrowing incidents and others listed in annex 1]

2. Literature Review

The contacts throughout history between the English language and Arabic generally support a mutual borrowing hypothesis such as scientific the borrowing in the form of old roots of names of flowers and plants of pharmaceuticals in English through the German language known to have been done through translation of Arabic written books in the renaissance period and the visiting scholars from Europe to Andalusia. The Norman conquest of Arabic speaking Sicily, the crusaders times, the British colonization of many Arab counties in the last centuries are reasons to support the borrowing theory. However, there are many other cognates that attest to a different relationship leaving only the proposed theory of immigration of Mesopotamian tribes towards the West whose language spread over Europe to explain such similarities of the many cognates systems between the two languages.

Therefore, the question of the origin of the English language is still not resolved yet. Many believe that around 50% of the English words relate to modern German, the remaining two-fourths to Latin and French. Alhashmi (2012) mentions that Austine Waddell, a British linguist as saying "*I was led by the facts to observe that the Sumerians were the early Aryans.... and that their written letters is derived from the Phoenician language scripts ...and that 50% of the commonest words in the English language today is discovered to be Sumerian in origin with the same word form , sound , and meaningemphasizing the proximity of Sumero-Phonecian languages to Arabic.*" p.593 .

The researcher avoided detailed analysis of the phonological features tying to be appealing to across the board audience of interested and concerned scholars.

2. Method

The researcher has analyzed the cognate systems finding consistent patterns. For examples, the vocabulary in both languages can be related easily to Arabic roots. The method of descriptive and contrastive analysis between Arabic and English was used to analyze the cognate systems.

3. Discussion and Results

Some linguists suggest that the word *Europe* is an Arabic word meaning *west* starting with the sound /gh/ replaced in one of the Arabic dialects with the a glottal stop as an allophone thus sounding exactly like the Arabic word /gharbeh/ meaning *west* indicating the direction of the people living in Europe from the point of view of the people in the south, modern Iraq or the Arab Peninsula.

Accidentally, I found one of the sources on the history of the English language proposing that the mother of the English language uses the word "*siex*" to mean *a big knife* which is known to be an Arabic word still used to mean the same, which triggered an interest to look at

the two languages' cognate systems which are affected by historic shifts, transformations but still recognizable for a bilingual Arabic native speaker:

First, **kin words**, it is known that many European languages are from Germanic origin known to use the words "father" as "fadre, faeter or vaeter" pronounced "faetter" in Arabic meaning "creator" (i.e. life giver) derived from the root "fater" thus explaining the disparities among Christian sects who believe the word "father" in English identifies the relationship between Jesus and God and other sects who still believe the word *father* in the bible refers to God. The word *mother* in English pronounced "modre" in European languages come from the root (dera) meaning *dispense* pronounced "mudereh" making a noun in Arabic meaning "milk dispenser" synonymous to "mother" in English but not mother any more in modern Arabic. In Arabic, most words are derived from 93 thousand roots allowing native speakers of Arabic to elicit the meaning of the derivatives of most words.

Second, old words such as **things or items, property** [eart(h) (ard), coffin-cup-house, table, fire, urn, candle, grave- qarafeh) are also good examples to support this theory. For example, the word "house" in English is pronounced "hawza" in German known to come from the Arabic word "hawza" with emphatic (h) which is a laryngeal sound, meaning the same in Arabic still used in modern Iraq. This example attests to the idea of migrations of tribes from Mesopotamia (present day Iraq) to north European lands, thus, for example, helping understand the origin of the word "hospital" *hawzabitar* in Iraqi Arabic dialect the "house of the physician". Later, the linguistic divergence caused by geographic distances contributed to the disparities among the many dialects of German language. **Animals**, too, such as [cat, bug, camel, gazelle] can attest to this purposed relationship as such words do not change overtime.

The third evidence is illustrated in the **article system** in English is similar to the **demonstrative pronoun system in Arabic** such as "the" or "thi" meaning "he/she consecutively who has" and "that" in Arabic meaning "she who has" and "thou" similar in meaning to "the". And, the **pronoun system** such as "who" for singular male and "whom" originally plural pronoun pronounced the same in Arabic and having the same function. Both of these systems are known to be non-susceptible to change, thus old enough in both languages to attest to the hypothesis.

The fourth evidence can be called a **linguistic one** such be equivalent to the pronominal female noun suffix in Arabic. The [e] sound dropped from the English language before gender differentiation in nouns was abolished in English, but still functioning in modern German. The *word order* of sentences of both language allowed the sentence to start with a verb until the seventeen hundreds when the English language dropped the verbal form in word order maintaining the nominal one. *Inflection-wise*, like the Arabic language, the German inflects the end part of the German words for gender at first, second and third person levels. Phonetically, both have 44 sounds representing the vowels and the consonants in both languages. The fifth evidence is also illustrated in certain **biological functions and parts**, such as "fart" from the Arabic word meaning "break out" and "fuss" which retained its meaning in Arabic to mean a loud *fart*. Regarding *body parts*, the words *eye, hoof, neck, waist, nasa, body, ass* are also body parts which are very similar to each other in both languages not expecting to change overtime.

The fifth evidence is the many **emphatic sounds** in Arabic illustrated in the double letters in English which lost its emphatic quality overtime; however, the quality of the two

letters such as “Ss” in the word “fuss” is considered an emphatic “s” sounding like that in Arabic. Also, the /x/ sound historically existed in the German language represented by [gh] in English but almost totally dropped from the English words ushering to a shared sound between both Arabic and the German languages not available in many world languages. Finally, we find that **numbers** in German sound very similar to the Arabic language.

The researcher expects this communication to be a spring board for a future thorough investigation of the proposed ideas awaiting the reaction of scholars to decide the direction of perusal of the theory.

4. Conclusion

The word Arabic is being used here to due to the similarities that are still very apparent in both languages. The researcher reached the conclusion of mother and daughter relationship between English and Arabic based on the cognate systems provided leaving little doubt that it is an origin relationship not simply borrowing of words as most have suggested.

About the author

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References

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Appendix 1

The following chart includes vocabulary cognate system with examples showing the similarities.

Tactic takhtit	تخطيط	Urn	جرن	Law	لوح
Typhoon-/Tufan/	طوفان	Wail	عويل	Machine / makan/	مكن
Tie /tay/	طي	Trafalgar	الطرف الأغر	Milk	ملىق
Waist /wasat/	وسط	Neck	/ unnk/ عنق	Schedule	جدول
Cotton kutun	قطن	algebra	الجبر	Admiral	امير البحر

Type Tab	طبع	Shame	سخام	Story / estory/	اسطوري
Add ad	عد	Surgery	سرج	Void	فاضي
Buy-sell Baay -sila	بيع- سلع	Talk	هلق	Pee	يال
Hurry	هرع	Guitar	قيثارة	Cough	كح
Play	يلعب	Hazard	حذر	Bio	بيو
Table / tabliyeh/	طبلية	Hello /Hala/	هلا	Kane	قناة
Traffic / fafrik/	تفريق	Ill	علة	Hallucination	هلوسة
Icon	ايقونة	Jasmine	ياسمين	Caliber	قالب
Jail	غل	Maneuver	مناورة	Castle /caser/	قصر
Kill	قتل	Almanac	مناخ	Corn / qarn/	قرن
Master	مسيطر	Canon	قانون	Dusk	غسق
Music	موسيقى	Wine	حانة	Down /dun/	دون
Antique	عتيق	Able / qabel/	قابل	Elite	علا
Apricot	برقوق	Act	عقد	Fire	فرن
Azure	لازورد	Ass /esst/	است	Girl	جارية
Bad	بديء	Bluff /Balaf/	بلف	Good	جيد
Candle /qandeel /	قنديل	Walk	ولق	Lingua Franca	لغة الفرنجة
Due	ديه	Dress	درز	Day	ضى
Dim	ضم	Dig	دق	Stand	استند
Ascend	سند	Sun	سنا	Camera	قمره
Grave	قرافه	Sugar	شجر	Furnish	فرش
Talk	طلق	Alchemy	الكيمياء	Carat	قيراط

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